

METHODICAL RECOMMENDATION ON THE USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract: This methodical recommendation contains a methodical recommendation on the use of pedagogical technology in the educational process in English language classes, in which the technology of teaching one subject is revealed.

Keywords: Pedagogical technology, teaching methods, student's activities, interactive means interacting, their interest...

Annotatsiya: Ushbu metodik tavsiya ingliz tili darslarida o'quv jarayonida pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish bo'yicha metodik tavsiyani o'z ichiga oladi, unda bitta fanni o'qitish texnologiyasi ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Pedagogik texnologiya, o'qitish usullari, talabalar faoliyati, interaktiv vositalar, ularning qiziqishi...

Relevance of the topic: enriching the knowledge of the English language of the young generation and teaching lessons using modern methods.

Purpose: To form knowledge and skills about the use of pedagogical technology in the educational process in English language classes.

Result: To develop students' thinking ability, listening comprehension, knowledge of grammatical topics.

Plan:

1. Technology of teaching English lessons through interactive methods.
2. Use of modern methods in teaching subjects
3. Pedagogical skill of the teacher in the lessons.

The use of any pedagogical technology in the educational process depends on the individual character, who is teaching the student and who is being taught by the teacher. Pedagogical technology in the educational process is an integral process in a clear sequence, it is a pedagogical process aimed at providing a goal-oriented, carefully planned and guaranteed result based on the needs of the student. The realization of the pedagogical goal and the achievement of a guaranteed result depends on the cooperative activity of the teacher and the student, the goal they set, the chosen content, style, form, tool, i.e. technology. It is up to the teacher and the student to choose the technology to achieve the goal, because the main goal of both parties is to achieve a specific result, and the technology used is chosen depending on the level of knowledge of the students, the character of the group, and the conditions. For example: in order to achieve the result, perhaps it is necessary to work with a computer, perhaps a film or handout, drawings and posters, information technology, various literature will be needed. It all depends on the teacher and students. The role and importance of modern teaching

methods - interactive methods, innovative technologies in the educational process is incomparable.

Pedagogical technology and knowledge of their use in education ensures that students acquire knowledge and advanced skills. Innovation means innovation. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and teacher's and student's activities, and interactive methods are mainly used in its implementation. Interactive means interacting or having a conversation with someone. In other words, interactive teaching methods are a special form of organizing knowledge and communicative activity, in which students are involved in the learning process, have the opportunity to understand and think about what they know and think. will be

"DESCRIPTIVE AND CREATIVE" METHOD.

Using this method, the class is divided into groups and assignments are given in advance. The groups are conventionally named, for example, "Describers" and "Creator" group. The first group gives the definitions to the second group. After that, the groups will find which creator this description belongs to. If, after the first given definition, they find out which writer or poet this definition belongs to, they get 5 points, if they find it after the second information, 4 points, and if they find it in the third attempt, they get 3 points. The teacher asks the group that found out which creator the definition belongs to, to add more information about the creator's life and work and assesses it. Through this method, every student will have the opportunity to participate.

Who am I?.

The teacher describes animals and pupils answer what animal it is. It is a cow.

Teacher: I have 2 long ears. I have tail, my colour is grey. I'm very hardworking animal. I say haw-hee-haw, haw-hee-haw. Who am I?

Pupils: Donkey

Teacher: my name is Masha. I give milk to kids. I eat green grass. I have 4 legs and tail. I say moo-moo-moo. Who am I?

The ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice is formed by teaching students to search, independently refer to additional sources, and to select the necessary materials from the data bank. In this, of course, a great responsibility is placed on the teacher, because they are based on the specific subject specified in the State educational standard, the curriculum and the textbook, as well as the specific aspects of the subject, the age and psychophysiological characteristics of the students. and form the elements of competences related to science and choose educational methods and lesson forms based on their interest.

"How old is your sister?"

Objectives: to recycle the family members; to consolidate the numbers.

STEP 1: Ask the pupils to work in pairs. Ask all the pupils to write about their real or imaginary family members' ages.

STEP 2: After writing family members' ages, Pupil 1 asks his/her partner and Pupil 2 answers as follows:

Pupil 1: 'how old is your sister?'

Pupil 2: 'she's 20. how old is your brother?'

Find the names of fast food in the table

So, the role of the teacher in interactive lessons leads to the directness of the students' activities to achieve the lesson goals. In this regard, the main attention in teaching English is focused on increasing students' vocabulary, forming their English speech, and developing the skills of correct pronunciation of speech sounds.

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